

Improved Photovoltaic Performance under Non-Uniform Irradiance Using Total Cross Tied Arrangement and Grid-Based Load Balancing

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KEYWORDS

Photovoltaic (PV) Array, Total Cross Tied (TCT) Configuration, Partial Shading Conditions, Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), Perturb and Observe (P&O) Algorithm, Grid Integration, Load Balancing.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the performance analysis of a photovoltaic (PV) array configuration under various partial shading conditions using the Total Cross Tied (TCT) interconnection scheme. The study aims to maximize power output and improve array efficiency in the presence of non-uniform irradiance. The TCT configuration offers superior shading tolerance through its combined horizontal and vertical interconnections, allowing for better current distribution and reduced mismatch losses compared to conventional series-parallel and bridge-linked configurations. To ensure uninterrupted energy supply and effective load management, the PV system is integrated with the utility grid, enabling dynamic load balancing. The grid supplement power during low PV generation periods and absorbs surplus power during high generation. A simulation model is developed to analyze the performance of the TCT-connected PV array under different shading scenarios, including corner, central, and diagonal patterns. To extract the maximum available power under fluctuating irradiance conditions, the Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is implemented. Simulation results confirm that the TCT configuration, when combined with the P&O MPPT technique, significantly enhances power extraction efficiency under partial shading. Furthermore, grid integration improves overall system reliability, making the proposed approach a viable solution for smart grid and renewable energy applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for sustainable and environmentally friendly energy sources has intensified research in the area of renewable energy technologies. Among them, photovoltaic (PV) systems have emerged as a reliable and scalable solution for clean electricity generation due to their modularity, silent operation, low maintenance requirements, and capability to harness abundant solar energy [1], [2]. However, the power output of PV systems is highly dependent on irradiance and temperature, making them vulnerable to environmental factors such as partial shading, which can significantly degrade performance [3], [4]. Partial shading, caused by obstructions like trees, buildings, clouds, or dirt accumulation, leads to non-uniform irradiance on the PV modules. This mismatch condition results in multiple local maxima on the power-voltage (P-V) curve and reduces the overall efficiency of the system [5], [6]. To minimize such losses, various PV array configurations have been explored, including Series-Parallel (SP), Bridge-Linked (BL), and Total Cross Tied (TCT) arrangements [7], [8]. Among these, the TCT configuration has been recognized as one of the most effective methods for mitigating shading effects, as it enhances current distribution and improves output power by electrically connecting modules in both horizontal and vertical directions [9], [10]. In a 3×3 PV array, the impact of partial shading is more prominent due to the limited number of interconnected paths. The TCT configuration in such a setup distributes the shading impact across multiple strings, reducing mismatch losses and improving the extraction of maximum power under various shading scenarios such as diagonal, corner, and central shading [11], [12]. Furthermore, to continuously track and extract the maximum power from the PV system, Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) techniques are essential. Among these, the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm is widely adopted due to its simplicity, ease of implementation, and cost-effectiveness [13], [14]. The P&O method works by incrementally perturbing the

operating voltage and observing the effect on output power, adjusting the reference voltage accordingly to achieve convergence to the maximum power point [15]. In addition to enhancing power output under partial shading, grid integration of PV systems plays a crucial role in stabilizing energy supply. When connected to the utility grid, the PV system can dynamically manage power flow, delivering surplus energy to the grid during peak generation and drawing power during deficits, thereby supporting load balancing and improving system reliability [16], [17]. This becomes particularly important in smart grid environments where distributed generation and demand-side management are key elements [18], [19]. Recent studies have demonstrated that combining optimized PV configurations with intelligent control strategies such as MPPT and grid-tied operation significantly enhances system resilience and energy yield [20], [21]. Advanced simulation tools like MATLAB/Simulink have been widely used to model such systems, analyze their behavior under real-world conditions, and evaluate their performance metrics such as power output, voltage stability, and efficiency [22], [23]. Moreover, integrating intelligent algorithms and fault-tolerant configurations is essential to maximize renewable energy utilization and reduce dependency on fossil fuels [24], [25]. This paper focuses on the implementation and analysis of a 3×3 PV array using the Total Cross Tied (TCT) configuration to extract maximum power under varying partial shading conditions. The system employs the Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT technique and is integrated with the utility grid to enable dynamic load sharing. Simulations are conducted for different shading patterns to assess the robustness and effectiveness of the proposed setup. The results demonstrate that the combination of TCT interconnection, MPPT, and grid support leads to improved energy extraction, reduced mismatch losses, and enhanced overall system stability, making it a suitable approach for modern renewable energy systems [26]-[30].

Fig. 1 proposed TCT connected modules of solar integrated with grid system

II. System Configuration

The proposed system architecture integrates a solar photovoltaic (PV) array configured in a Total Cross Tied (TCT) interconnection scheme, which is known for its improved performance under partial shading conditions due to its combination of series and parallel connections both horizontally and vertically. The array consists of nine PV modules arranged in a 3×3 matrix, where each row is connected in series and each column is cross-tied, enabling better current distribution and reduced mismatch losses. This arrangement allows the system to maintain higher power output even when parts of the array are subjected to shading caused by environmental obstacles like clouds, trees, or buildings. To ensure optimal energy harvesting from the PV array, a Perturb and Observe (P&O) based Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is implemented. The MPPT controller continuously adjusts the operating point of the PV array by perturbing the voltage and monitoring the resulting changes in power output, thereby enabling the system to operate close to its maximum power point at all times. The PV array is interfaced with the power grid, allowing the system to export excess energy during high solar generation and import energy during periods of insufficient solar availability, thereby supporting dynamic load balancing and enhancing system reliability. This grid-tied configuration ensures a stable and uninterrupted power supply to connected loads, while also promoting efficient utilization of renewable energy resources. The combination of the TCT configuration, P&O MPPT technique, and grid integration makes the proposed system highly effective

for smart grid and sustainable energy applications, particularly in scenarios with varying irradiance and partial shading.

III. Modeling and designing proposed solar PV system configuration

Photovoltaic (PV) cells generate voltage when sunlight is incident on them. It is the basic building block for converting solar energy into electrical energy. Fig. 2(a) represents the equivalent circuit of PV cells as one diode model [19]. The circuit consists of a current generated by incident solar insolation called photo current (I_{ph}), a diode, a parallel resistance (R_{sh}) and a series resistance (R_s) representing the leakage current and an internal resistance respectively of the PV cell [20]. Each PV cell generates a small voltage of 0.6 V. These cells are connected in series and in parallel to increase the module voltage and module current respectively. Figure 2(b) represents the equivalent circuit of the PV module with N_p cells connected in parallel and N_s cells connected in series. The mathematical equations that describes the I-V characteristics of PV cell are given by (1) to (4).

$$I_{pv} = I_{ph} - I_d - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{ph} = I_{sc} + k_i(T - 298)H \quad (2)$$

$$I_d = I_o \left[\exp\left(\frac{(V + I_{pv}R_s)q}{AKT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V + I_{pv}R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

where I_{pv} is the terminal current of the PV cell; I_{ph} is the current generated by the incident solar irradiance, I_d is the diode current and I_{sh} is the shunt resistance current; I_{sc} is the short circuit current of the cell, K_i is the array

short circuit current temperature coefficient, T is the cell operating temperature (K), H is the solar radiation in KW/m^2 ; I_0 is the diode reverse leakage current, V is the terminal voltage, K is Boltzmann's constant ($1.3806503 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K}$) [21], q is the electron charge ($1.60217646 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$); R_{sh} and R_s are the shunt and series resistances of the PV cell in Ω and A is the diode ideality factor and its ideal value is 1. The mathematical equation that describes the I-V characteristics of PV module is given by (5) [1]:

Fig. 2. (a) Equivalent circuit model of PV cell, (b) Equivalent circuit of PV module.

$$I_m = N_p I_{ph} - N_p I_0 \left[\exp \left(\frac{q}{AKT} \left(\frac{V_m}{N_s} + \frac{I_m R_s}{N_p} \right) \right) - 1 \right] - \frac{N_p V_m + I_m R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (5)$$

where I_m is the terminal current of the PV module; V_m is the terminal voltage of the PV module. PV module is modeled in MATLAB/Simulink to obtain the I-V and P-V characteristics. Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b) represent the I-V and P-V characteristics of the PV module for different insolation conditions.

IV. TERMS AND DEFINITIONS PERTAINING TO THE PV ARRAY

1. Photovoltaic (PV) Cell: The fundamental unit that converts sunlight into electricity using the photovoltaic effect. No specific formula, but its output current and voltage depend on irradiance and temperature.

- PV Module: An assembly of multiple PV cells connected in series and/or parallel to achieve the desired voltage and current output.
- PV Array: A larger combination of multiple PV modules connected to form a power-generating surface. The total output depends on the connection:

$$V_{total} = \sum V_i,$$

$$I_{total} = I_i$$

$$I_{total} = \sum I_i,$$

$$V_{total} = V_i$$

- Total Cross Tied (TCT) Configuration: A hybrid configuration where modules are connected both horizontally in series and vertically in parallel. It enhances shading tolerance and allows better current distribution.
- Mismatch Losses: Occur when non-identical modules are connected, often due to partial shading. Power loss due to mismatch is given by:

$$P_{loss} = P_{ideal} - P_{actual} \quad (6)$$

- Partial Shading: A condition when parts of the PV array are shaded, reducing current and possibly creating multiple peaks in the power-voltage (P-V) curve.
- Bypass Diode: Connected in parallel with PV modules or strings to bypass shaded modules and avoid hot spots. It prevents current from flowing through shaded or faulty modules.

- Open Circuit Voltage (V_{oc}): The maximum voltage when no current flows:

$$V_{oc} = V_T \ln \left(\frac{I_{ph}}{I_0} + 1 \right) \quad (7)$$

Where: $V_T = \frac{nkT}{q}$ (thermal voltage), I_{ph} = photo generated current, I_0 = saturation current.

- Short Circuit Current (I_{sc}): The current when the module terminals are shorted ($V = 0$):

$$I_{sc} \approx I_{ph} \quad (8)$$

- Maximum Power Point (MPP): The point on the P-V curve where power is maximum:

$$P_{max} = V_{mpp} \times I_{mpp} \quad (9)$$

- Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT): A control algorithm (like P&O) used to find and maintain operation at MPP under varying conditions.

- Fill Factor (FF): Indicates the squareness of the I-V curve and quality of the module:

$$FF = \frac{P_{max}}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} = \frac{V_{mpp} \times I_{mpp}}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} \quad (10)$$

- Efficiency (η): Ratio of output power to the input solar power:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \times 100 = \frac{V_{mpp} \times I_{mpp}}{A \times G} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

Where: A = area of the module (m²), G = solar irradiance (W/m²).

V. Solar Boost Converter with P&O MPPT Algorithm

A boost converter is a power electronic circuit used in solar photovoltaic systems to step up the voltage generated by the solar panel. Since the output voltage of a PV module is often lower than what is required for grid connection or to power DC loads, a boost converter increases the voltage to a usable level. It includes an inductor, a power switch such as a MOSFET, a diode, and an output capacitor. When the switch is turned on, the inductor stores energy from the PV panel. When the switch is turned off, the inductor releases this energy to the load through the diode, resulting in a higher output voltage. By adjusting the amount of time the switch remains on and off, referred to as the duty cycle, the output voltage can be controlled. The boost converter ensures that maximum energy from the solar panel is transferred efficiently, making it an essential component in solar power systems.

Fig. 3 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

a. P&O MPPT Algorithm

The P&O MPPT algorithm adjusts the duty cycle (D) of the boost converter based on small perturbations to the PV voltage. The power change is determined as follows:

$$\Delta P = P(k) - P(k-1) \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta V = V(k) - V(k-1) \quad (13)$$

if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, increase V_{pv}

if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V > 0$, decrease V_{pv}

if $\Delta P > 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, decrease V_{pv} (14)

if $\Delta P < 0$ and $\Delta V < 0$, increase V_{pv}

The updated duty cycle is calculated as:

$$D(k+1) = D(k) + \alpha \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta P) \quad (15)$$

Where α is the step size for duty cycle adjustment.

Fig. 4 flow chart for P&O MPPT algorithm

b. Boost Converter Design

The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC bus voltage. The output voltage of the boost converter is given by:

Fig. 5 DC-DC unidirectional boost converter

$$V_o = \frac{V_{pv}}{1-D} \quad (16)$$

Where: V_o = Output voltage of boost converter (V), V_{pv} = Input PV voltage (V), D = Duty cycle of the converter

The inductor value is selected to ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation:

$$L = \frac{V_{pv}(1-D)}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (17)$$

where: L = Inductor value (H), f_s = Switching frequency (Hz), ΔI_L = Inductor ripple current (A)

The output capacitor is designed to minimize voltage ripples:

$$C = \frac{I_o}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_o} \quad (18)$$

Where: C = Output capacitor (F), I_o = Output current (A), ΔV_o = Allowable voltage ripple (V)

VI. Modeling and Design of a Grid-Connected Voltage Source Converter (VSC) Controller

A bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) plays a crucial role in integrating renewable energy systems, electric vehicle charging stations, and microgrids by enabling efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC link as shown in Fig.8. The d-q current control strategy is widely used to regulate

power flow, improve power quality, and maintain DC link voltage stability. The system operates under a synchronous reference frame (SRF) to ensure precise control of active and reactive power components.

Fig.6 designing of bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter

The control operation of the grid-connected bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) is based on a hierarchical structure comprising DC-link voltage regulation, current control, grid synchronization, and bidirectional power flow management. The DC-link voltage regulation is achieved through an outer-loop PI controller, which maintains the reference DC voltage by adjusting the d-axis current reference (I_{d_ref}). This ensures a stable DC bus, crucial for efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC load. The inner-loop current controllers regulate the d-axis and q-axis currents to track their respective reference values, enabling precise control over active and reactive power (P-Q regulation). A Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is employed for grid synchronization, ensuring that the converter operates in phase with the grid voltage, which is essential for stable operation under varying grid conditions as shown in Fig.9. The bidirectional operation of the converter allows seamless transition between grid-to-DC charging (rectifier mode) and DC-to-grid discharging (inverter mode) depending on the power flow direction. In rectifier mode, the converter draws power from the grid to maintain the required DC voltage, whereas in inverter mode, it injects power back into the grid when excess DC power is available. This comprehensive control strategy ensures optimal power management, enhances grid stability, and improves the overall efficiency of the system.

1. Mathematical Modeling of the Bidirectional AC-DC VSC

The operation of the bidirectional VSC can be described using d-q axis equations derived from Kirchhoff's Voltage Law (KVL). The system consists of an LC filter, a

three-phase inverter, and a DC-link capacitor, ensuring stable voltage conversion.

1.1 AC Side d-q Equations

The AC-side dynamics of the three-phase VSC in the synchronous rotating reference frame are given by:

$$V_d = R_s I_d + L_s \frac{dI_d}{dt} - \omega L_s I_q + V_{gd} \quad (19)$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + L_s \frac{dI_q}{dt} - \omega L_s I_d + V_{gq} \quad (20)$$

where:

- V_d, V_q = d-q axis voltages at the converter terminals
- I_d, I_q = d-q axis currents
- R_s, L_s = Resistance and inductance of the filter
- ω = Synchronous angular frequency
- V_{gd}, V_{gq} = d-q components of the grid voltage

The active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injected into the grid are given by:

$$P = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) \quad (21)$$

$$Q = \frac{3}{2} (V_q I_d - V_d I_q) \quad (22)$$

2. DC-Link Voltage Controller Design

The DC-link voltage (V_{dc}) is regulated using a PI controller to ensure stable operation during bidirectional power transfer. The power balance at the DC bus is given by:

$$C_{dc} \frac{dV_{dc}}{dt} = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) - P_{dc_load} \quad (23)$$

where: C_{dc} = DC-link capacitor, P_{dc_load} = Power consumed by the DC load

To maintain a stable DC-link voltage, a PI controller is implemented as:

$$I_d^{ref} = K_p (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) + K_i \int (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) dt \quad (24)$$

where: K_p, K_i = Proportional and integral gains of the PI controller, I_{dref} = Reference d-axis current

3. d-q Current Controller Design

The d-axis and q-axis current controllers regulate the power exchange between the converter and the grid.

3.1 d-Axis Current Controller (Active Power Control)

The d-axis current controller regulates the active power (P) supplied to or drawn from the grid. The reference current is obtained from the DC-link voltage controller:

$$I_d^{ref} = \frac{P^{ref}}{1.5V_d} \quad (25)$$

Using a PI compensator, the d-axis voltage command is:

$$V_d^{ref} = K_p^d (I_d^{ref} - I_d) + K_i^d \int (I_d^{ref} - I_d) dt \quad (26)$$

Where K_p^d, K_i^d are PI gains

3.2 q-Axis Current Controller (Reactive Power Control)

The q-axis current controller regulates reactive power (Q), and the reference current is:

$$I_d^{ref} = \frac{Q^{ref}}{1.5V_q} \quad (27)$$

The q-axis voltage command is:

$$V_d^{ref} = K_p^q (I_q^{ref} - I_q) + K_i^q \int (I_q^{ref} - I_q) dt \quad (28)$$

Where K_p^q, K_i^q are PI gains

Fig. 7 Grid conversion controller

VII. Results and Discussion

A. TCT-Connected PV Array under Partial Shading with MPPT and Grid Integration

The simulation of the proposed 3×3 PV array using the Total Cross Tied (TCT) configuration was carried out in MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate performance under various partial shading conditions. Under uniform irradiance, the array delivered maximum power output with stable voltage, and the P&O MPPT algorithm quickly tracked the optimal power point. When partial shading patterns such as diagonal, corner, and central shading were applied, the TCT configuration showed superior performance compared to traditional Series-Parallel and Bridge-Linked setups. In diagonal shading, current redistribution through the TCT layout reduced mismatch losses, while the MPPT continued to function accurately. During corner and central shading, although power output dropped slightly due to reduced irradiance, the TCT structure allowed alternate current paths to maintain relatively high efficiency. The integration with the grid enabled dynamic load balancing, where excess energy was exported to the grid during high generation, and power was drawn from the grid when PV output dropped. The system maintained voltage and current quality within acceptable limits, and the THD levels remained low, ensuring power quality compliance. These results confirm that the combination of TCT interconnection, P&O MPPT, and grid integration enhances PV performance and system reliability even in non-uniform irradiance conditions.

Fig. 8 Simulation Results of TCT-Connected PV Array under Partial Shading with MPPT and Grid Integration

B. Dynamic Load and Power Management under Variable Solar Irradiation

The simulation was conducted to analyze dynamic load and power management in a 3×3 Total Cross Tied (TCT) photovoltaic array under varying solar irradiation conditions. The total solar capacity was set at 45 kW, while the connected load demanded 35 kW. Under standard irradiation conditions (1000 W/m²), the system generated sufficient power to meet the entire load demand, and surplus energy was exported to the grid. However, as solar irradiation gradually decreased from 1000 W/m² to 0 W/m², a significant drop in power output was observed. Despite the reduction in irradiance due to partial shading, the TCT configuration maintained efficient current redistribution and minimized mismatch losses. The Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT algorithm ensured that the PV system continuously tracked the maximum available power. During low irradiance or zero irradiance scenarios, when the PV output dropped below the 35 kW load requirement, the grid dynamically compensated by supplying the power deficit, ensuring uninterrupted load operation. The transition between PV supply and grid support occurred smoothly without voltage fluctuations, indicating effective coordination and load sharing. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the TCT configuration in managing partial shading, while the grid integration significantly enhances system stability and reliability during dynamic irradiance variations.

Fig. 9 Simulation Results of Dynamic Load and Power Management under Variable Solar Irradiation in a TCT-Connected PV System

Fig.10 Grid current THD

VIII. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the integration of a 3×3 photovoltaic array using the Total Cross Tied (TCT) configuration, coupled with the Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm and grid-based dynamic load management, offers significant advantages under partial shading conditions. The TCT arrangement effectively reduces mismatch losses by redistributing current through multiple parallel paths, thereby maintaining higher power output compared to conventional configurations such as Series-Parallel and Bridge-Linked. Simulation results under various shading scenarios, including diagonal, corner, and central patterns, confirm that the proposed system maintains stable voltage levels and reliable power delivery. Furthermore, the seamless integration with the utility grid ensures continuous load support by supplying excess power during high irradiance and drawing power during generation deficits. This dual capability enhances system flexibility, reliability, and resilience, making the proposed approach highly suitable for smart grid applications and modern distributed renewable energy systems.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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